

MATERIAL CHARACTERISATION OF A COMPOSITE USING MICRO-CT IMAGE-BASED FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

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SUMMARY

Generating high quality computational models from CT or MicroCT scan data presents itself as a valuable technique for the investigation of physical phenomena. This paper utilizes CT data as the NDE technique to characterize the initial matrix porosity's locations and sizes in a Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMC) test specimen.

Keywords: Finite Element Analysis, Computed Tomography, Ceramic matrix Composites, Stress Analysis, Non Destructive Evaluation

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL GENERATION

Novel techniques for generating robust and accurate meshes based on 3D imaging data have recently been developed which make the prediction of macro-structural properties of composite structures based on micro-structural composition straightforward. These new techniques have been applied to the analysis of a ceramic matrix composite (CMC) material with matrix voids, which was microCT scanned and the influence of imaging parameters on both predicted bulk properties and localized stresses has been explored.

CMC Specimen

In this study, dog bone shaped specimens were extracted from a panel made out of a CMC material, which consists of 40% Sylaromic fiber, 6-7% porosity, Boron Nitride (BN) internal coating, 20-25% Chemical Vapor Infiltrated (CVD)-SiC coating, and Melted Infiltrate (MI) matrix. The material was fatigue tested and CT scanned before and after cycling to characterise the initial matrix porosity's distribution and sizes.

Scan and Mesh Generation

For this study, 20 2D slices of around 0.2 mm were required, given the accuracy of the CT system used in this study. The in-plane resolution of the scanner was 0.2mm (in both X and Y directions), whereas the separation between each slice was 1.25 mm. Structural deformities such as surface roughness of the matrix as well as other internal critical anomalies are depicted in the 3D rendered model. Figure 1 shows a CT scan of

the CMC, as well as rendered model illustrating various anomalies within the ceramic materials.

Figure 1 CT scan of CMC material (a), rendered view with detail of holes (b).

ScanIP and +ScanFE (Simpleware Ltd.) were used to generate a number of finite element meshes based on the 3D segmented image data. The anti-aliasing techniques implemented ensure high accuracy of reconstruction; unlike many smoothing schemes they are volume, topology and geometry preserving ensuring models whose geometric accuracy is contingent only on image quality Figure 2 shows a model which represents a view of the mesh.

Figure 2 Model of the mesh in point cloud view.

Finite Element Analysis

A series of FE analyses were carried out to calculate the localised stress field around the pores based on the geometric modelling of the specimen's CT results. The finite element analysis shown in Figure 3 indicated that the stress risers in the composite are located at expected sites such as porosities and voids locations. The work demonstrates that FE models based on an accurate 3D model from CT data are an essential tool to quantify the effects of internal defects in complex material systems such as CMCs.

Figure 3 Stress distribution showing critical regions / high stress risers.